

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF BIOFUELS PRODUCTION IN UKRAINE

Zheliezna T.,
Drahniev S.

*Institute of Engineering Thermophysics of the National Academy of Sciences
Ukraine*

03057, Marii Kapnist Street, 2a, Kyiv

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11114266>

Abstract

The purpose of the article is to consider results of a feasibility study of biofuels production in Ukraine and to determine the most promising types of motor biofuels for the country. The performed techno-economic assessment covers bioethanol and biodiesel from different types of feedstocks as well as hydrotreated vegetable oil. The study includes analysis of the potential of biomass available for the production of biofuels and energy in Ukraine. Factors for a possible growth of the potential in a long-term period are considered. The demand for motor biofuels in the country and their export potential are analysed. To determine feasible types of projects, techno-economic assessment of biofuels production in Ukraine's conditions has been performed. The obtained results show that under the current circumstances, some projects are much more feasible than the others, the simple payback period of the projects being 3-4 to 6-9 years. Based on analysis of relevant international studies, available biomass potential in Ukraine and results of the performed feasibility study, some prospective types of motor biofuels for the production and consumption in Ukraine have been determined. To support further development of this sector it is necessary to introduce some additional incentives on the state level.

Keywords: biomass, biofuels, bioethanol, biodiesel, feasibility study.

Introduction.

Decarbonisation of economy and energy is a global challenge of the present time caused by the necessity to mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and hold down the process of climate change. The European Green Deal is the main current strategy of the EU focused on achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Present contribution of the transport sector to the EU's total GHG emissions is 25% with the rising tendency. To reach the 2050 goal of carbon neutrality in Europe, a considerable, up to 90% reduction of GHG emissions in transport should be attained. The emphasis is on road transport, aviation sector and maritime sector. Boosting the production and use of biofuels in these sectors is an important part of the ambitious transport strategy within the European Green Deal (Chiaromonti 2021, Lundberg 2023, Tsakalidis 2020). For example, it is planned to reduce emissions from cars by 55% and emissions from vans by 50% by 2030 as well as provide zero emissions from new cars by 2035. To promote the consumption of sustainable aviation fuels (SAF), the minimum share of SAF required for blending with kerosene by European suppliers of aviation fuel has been increased. To give an incentive for using renewable and low-carbon marine fuels, a goal to gradually reduce the annual average GHG intensity of energy used by ships has been set.

Main provisions of the EU Renewable Energy Directive 2018 (RED II) regarding the transport sector were generally in line with the European Green Deal transport policy. The main mandatory goal was to reach at least 14% of renewable energy in the final energy consumption in transport. At that, the Directive promoted the production of advanced biofuels, that is biofuels obtained from lignocellulosic material, non-food

cellulosic material, biomass fraction of municipal and industrial waste and other types of feedstocks listed in Part A of Annex IX of RED II (Dusser 2019, Panoutsou 2021). The new version of the Renewable Energy Directive adopted in 2023 (RED III) allows the Member States to choose between a transport target expressed as a GHG intensity reduction (at least 14.5% by 2030) or as a share of renewable energy consumption in the transport sector (at least 29% by 2030). RED III encourages the production of advanced biofuels and its use in road transport, aviation and maritime transport. It is expected that the list of feedstocks for obtaining advanced biofuels, which is now under consideration, will be specified and expanded in RED III.

Being a member of Energy Community on its way to European integration, Ukraine is gradually implementing main provisions of Renewable Energy Directives. One of them applies to the introduction of renewable energy, including biofuels, in the transport sector. The National Transport Strategy of Ukraine until 2030 establishes a target to achieve 50% consumption of biofuels and electricity (renewable and traditional) in the total energy consumption in transport. The same target is stated in the draft National Energy and Climate Plan of Ukraine for 2025-2030. Such an ambitious goal can be reached only with a considerable contribution of biofuels.

Methodology.

Feasibility study of biofuels production should be started with analysis of Ukraine's biomass potential. Existing assessments show that Ukraine has a big potential of biomass available for energy production. This is probably one of the most important preconditions for the development of bioenergy sector in the country and replacement of expensive fossil fuels (Geletukha 2021,

Geletukha 2022). The economic potential of biomass is assessed at nearly 26 Mtoe/y with the biggest contribution from agricultural residues (42% of the total) and energy crops (21%) (Tryboi 2023, Zheliezna 2024). By 2050, the biomass potential may increase to about 44 Mtoe/y due to a number of factors, the main of which are possible increase in the yield of main agricultural crops; possible expansion of area under energy crops; development of sustainable growing intermediate/cover crops as feedstock for the production of biogas/biomethane.

Analysis and comparison of European and Ukrainian statistical data on agriculture shows that Ukraine still has room for increasing the yield of some cereal crops (for example, wheat and maize) by at least 1.2-1.25 times. Besides, Ukraine has quite a big area of permanently unused agricultural land (about 3 million hectares) that can be partly utilised for growing energy crops such as willow, poplar, miscanthus, camelina, maize (silage). Biomass of the energy crops can be used as feedstock for the sustainable production of solid, liquid and gaseous biofuels. A new promising direction of bioenergy development in Ukraine is growing intermediate/cover crops to obtain biomass for biogas/biomethane production. Bioenergy experts are now actively studying this issue. It should be noted that another important research area attracting increasingly more attention in the country is the production of synthetic renewable methane (Klimenko 2023).

Due to some obstacles, current production of liquid biofuels in Ukraine is very low being represented only by first-generation bioethanol. Nevertheless, analysis of structure and volume of the current and prospective biomass potential in the country indicates good prerequisites for the production of different motor biofuels including advanced ones. Now, it is a question of

biodiesel and bioethanol for road transport; however, in the postwar period it is necessary to study the matter of biofuels for aviation (SAF) and for waterborne transport (biodiesel, Fischer-Tropsch diesel, bio-oil of biomass fast pyrolysis) (Zheliezna 2022).

Analysis of international theoretical and practical studies indicates the following leading-edge technologies for further research and development:

- Production of advanced bioethanol and Fischer-Tropsch diesel from lignocellulosic feedstock.
- Production of hydrotreated vegetable oil (renewable diesel fuel).
- Production of sustainable aviation fuels such as synthesized paraffinic kerosene (SPK) from hydroprocessed esters and fatty acids, alcohol to jet SPK, Fischer-Tropsch hydroprocessed SPK.

This article considers only motor biofuels for road transport while further studies surely should cover the issues of sustainable fuels for aviation and waterborne transport.

In addition to the biomass potential, the feasibility study of biofuels production should take into account the demand for motor biofuels in Ukraine. This demand is mainly determined by combination of the current consumption of petrol and diesel and existing technical constrains for replacing them with bioethanol and biodiesel, respectively. The consumption of main motor fuels in Ukraine during 2017-2021 was quite stable with some small fluctuations: petrol 1.7-2.0 Mt/y, diesel fuel 5.1-5.8 Mt/y. At that, the use of liquefied propane and butane increased from 0.89 Mt in 2017 to 1.3 Mt in 2021 (Table 1). Statistical data for the period later than 2021 are not available because they are not published due to the state of martial law in the country.

Table 1.

Consumption of motor fuels in Ukraine.

Fuel type	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Motor petrol, Mt	2.0	1.8	1.7	1.8	2.0
Gas oils (diesel fuel), Mt	5.1	5.4	5.8	5.2	5.7
Liquefied propane and butane, Mt	0.89	1.0	1.2	1.4	1.3

Based on data on the use of motor fuels in Ukraine in 2021, the volume of domestic market for bioethanol can be estimated as 210 kt/y (on condition of blending 10% vol. bioethanol with petrol), and that for biodiesel is 290 kt/year (on condition of blending 5% vol. biodiesel with diesel fuel). In case of production of hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO), the volume of its use in Ukraine's domestic market can be much larger, since the properties of HVO allow its use as direct substitute for diesel fuel (Soo-Young 2014). Besides, if there is a large number of flex-fuel vehicles in use in Ukraine, the volume of bioethanol consumption in domestic market will also be considerably higher. The design of flex-fuel vehicles allows their running on petrol mixed with up to 50-85% bioethanol (Delavarrafiee 2018).

Bioethanol is used as an oxygen-containing additive to petrol, diesel or as a biologically renewable alternative substitute for petrol. When added to petrol, it increases its octane number and saturates it with oxygen, which leads to more complete combustion and a

reduction in emissions of harmful substances. From the chemical point of view, biodiesel is a mixture of fatty acid methyl ethers (FAME) of vegetable oils that contain 11% of oxygen, while diesel fuel and HVO are hydrocarbons that do not contain oxygen. Due to its oxygen content, FAME has a lower calorific value resulting in higher biofuel consumption as compared to traditional diesel fuel. Diesel fuel comprises aromatic hydrocarbons while HVO consists only of fully saturated paraffinic hydrocarbons. Cetane number and lower calorific value of HVO is higher than those of diesel and FAME. Applications of FAME under a cold weather are limited due to poorer low temperature properties as compared to the conventional diesel and HVO.

It is expected that the amount of potentially produced biofuels that exceeds Ukraine's domestic demand may be exported. First of all, this applies to advanced (second-generation) biofuels as they are sustainable. Sustainability of biofuels that are exported can

be confirmed by a relevant certification system, for example, by ISCC (International Sustainability and Carbon Certification). Such certification is obligatory for biofuels that are exported to the EU and voluntary for biofuels that are exported to countries outside the EU.

According to McKinsey & Company's forecast made in 2022, the global demand for sustainable motor fuels will grow to about 220 Mt/y until 2035 with a subsequent decrease to the level of 2025 (about 170 Mt/y) (Figure 1). By 2050, the largest increase in demand is expected for sustainable fuels from lignocellulosic feedstock (Figure 2). At that, there will remain quite a large demand for fuel from oils of edible crops. It is predicted that in 2030, the largest importers of bioethanol will be Brazil, the USA, Japan, Canada, the United Kingdom, and importers of biodiesel will be the EU, the USA, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Peru. The

general situation may remain approximately the same also for some period after 2030.

Taking into account the above data and forecasts, we have elaborated a middle-term scenario for the production of motor biofuels in Ukraine (Table 2) (Zheliezna 2023). The scenario covers first- and second-generation biodiesel and bioethanol from different types of feedstocks, which takes into consideration the available biomass potential in Ukraine. After 2035 it seems reasonable to gradually switch from the production of biodiesel to HVO as well as to restrict the production of first-generation bioethanol in favour of advanced biofuel. In general, the suggested basic scenario is in line with the draft National Energy and Climate Plan of Ukraine for 2025-2030 that also envisages the production of first- and second-generation biofuels.

Figure 1. Global sustainable fuel demand by sectors until 2050, Mt.

Figure 2. Global sustainable fuel demand by feedstock type until 2050, Mt.

Table 2.

Basic scenario for the production of motor biofuels in Ukraine until 2035, kt.

Biofuel type	2025	2030	2035
Biodiesel from:			
- rapeseed	56	113	226
- used cooking oil (UCO)	6	11	23
- unconditioned oils, vegetable and animal fats	0.2	0.5	0.9
- fats from livestock and poultry slaughter	6	8	11
- oil energy crops (advanced biofuel)	11	56	113
Bioethanol from:			
- maize grain	109	202	312
- molasses (advanced biofuel)	55	62	70
- residues of grain maize production (advanced biofuel)	31	78	234

Main part.

Feasibility might be a crucial aspect of biofuel production, which depends on maturity of a certain technology, cost of feedstock and other input materials and energy, possible sale price of the main product and by-products. An important feature of a biofuel production technology is its materials and energy intensity. Technologies for the production of first-generation biofuels are well established and worked out, though they may be less sustainable as compared to advanced (second-generation) biofuels in terms of GHG emissions.

Advanced biofuels are sustainable as they are obtained from waste and nonedible raw materials. However, the respective technologies are very complex and

the final product may be too expensive to be competitive with traditional motor fuels. In addition to the main product (a biofuel), there can be one or more by-products which are of interest of the market. For example, dried distillers grains (DDG) and maize oil are by-products in case of bioethanol production from maize grain (Table 3). When producing advanced bioethanol, the process generates its own energy for use in the process. The required input energy can be obtained from the lignocellulosic feedstock residues (unreacted biomass), and the surplus energy can be sold to gain additional income.

Table 3.

Mass balance for the production of motor biofuels.

Inputs and outputs	Bioethanol from maize grain	Advanced bioethanol from lignocellulosic feedstock	Biodiesel from vegetable oil	Biodiesel from UCO	HVO
Inputs to obtain 1 litre of a biofuel:					
Feedstock, kg	2.4	3.38	0.893	0.977	0.97
Chemicals, kg	-	0.38	Methanol 0.086	Methanol 0.087	Hydrogen 0.035
Power, kWh	0.20	-	0.036	0.08	0.085
Natural gas, MJ	7	-	0.93	1.71	0.27
Outputs:					
Biofuel (1 litre), kg	0.79	0.79	0.88	0.88	0.77
By-products, kg	DDG 0.72 Maize oil 0.03	Power 0.70 kWh	Glycerine 0.09	Glycerine 0.09	Fuel gas 0.03 Bio-propane 0.025 Naphtha 0.06

It should be noted that techno-economic assessment of biofuels production in Ukraine's conditions has been performed with detailed consideration of the relevant mass balances, especially regarding the input of required chemicals. The obtained results show that some projects are more feasible than the others. Simple

payback period (SPP) within 4 years may be achieved when producing bioethanol from maize grain and biodiesel from UCO (Table 4). These projects have the lowest capital expenses (CAPEX) and operating expenses (OPEX) of the considered options.

Table 4.

Results of feasibility study of biofuels production in Ukraine's conditions.

Indicators	Bioethanol from maize grain	Bioethanol from straw	Biodiesel from rapeseed oil	Biodiesel from UCO	HVO (rapeseed oil)
Production output, kt/y	50	50	50	20	100
Operational time, h/y	8000				
Expenses:					
Feedstock consumption, kt/y	152	214	50.7	22.2	126
Feedstock purchase price, EUR/t without VAT	102	50	810	300	810
Feedstock cost, mln EUR	15.5	30.4	45.1	8.7	120.2
CAPEX, mln EUR	32.3	139.3	32.0	26.6	112.0
OPEX, mln EUR/y	23.8	39.0	49.0	11.1	131.4
Biofuel production expenses, EUR/l	0.376	0.616	0.86	0.49	1.012
Depreciation charges, EUR/l	0.020	0.088	0.023	0.047	0.034
Income:					
Sale price of by-products, EUR/t without VAT	DDG 133.2 Maize oil 629.7	Power 0.079 EUR/kWh	Crude glycerine 100	Crude glycerine 100	Bio-propane 1041 Naphtha 528 Fuel gas 646
Income from sale of by-products, mln EUR/y	DDG 6.1 Maize oil 1.2	Power 3.5	Crude glycerine 0.51	Crude glycerine 0.20	Bio-propane 3.38 Naphtha 4.1 Fuel gas 2.5
Biofuel net cost, EUR/l	0.28	0.65	0.88	0.53	0.97
Biofuel sale price*, EUR/l without VAT	0.55	1.0	0.98	0.98	1.2
Economic performance indicators:					
Loan share of CAPEX, %	70				
Lending period, years	5				
Loan rate in EUR, %	6				
Internal return rate (IRR), %	45%	13.3%	17.3%	33.7%	19.9%
Simple payback period, years	3.3	8.5	6.8	4.0	6.3

* The price does not take into account the excise tax of 100 EUR/1000 l.

Obtaining bioethanol from lignocellulosic feedstock (such as straw) is a complex technology, therefore capital expenditures are high. As a result, SPP is more than 8 years despite comparatively low price of the feedstock (straw). Nevertheless, as such technologies are developing and improving, one can expect a noticeable decrease in the production cost of cellulosic bioethanol even in a short-term period. A promising direction for future research and development may be also obtaining advanced bioethanol from organic fraction of municipal solid waste [19].

As opposed to straw and other crop residues, rapeseed oil is an expensive feedstock, which negatively affects the biodiesel production projects (SPP is about 7 years). A possible solution can be switching over to a cheaper feedstock, for example, oil energy crops. UCO is not suited for this purpose as its amount is rather limited and collection is not well organized in Ukraine. Oil energy crops can be cultivated on permanently unused agricultural land (about 3 mln ha in Ukraine), which is

considered a sustainable approach to obtaining feedstock for biofuels. Another approach to improve feasibility could be the introduction of state subsidy or other type of support for producers of biofuels, especially the advanced ones. Now the only incentive is a zero-excise tax for bioethanol that is used for the production of blended petrol and for bioethanol that is exported. Obviously, it is not enough for the further development of the sector.

Findings.

Decarbonisation of the transport sector is an important part of the global GHG emissions mitigation. The problem is that it is rather difficult to decarbonize this sector, especially freight transportation, as compared to other energy sectors such as heat and power production. One of the possible directions is switching over from the traditional motor fuels to biofuels. Advanced biofuels are especially effective as their use leads to high reduction of CO₂ emission as compared to the consumption of petrol and diesel.

Based on complex analysis of international studies

and results of the performed techno-economic assessment for Ukraine's conditions, we consider a number of biofuels to be prospective for the country's transport sector. They include bioethanol from maize grain, bioethanol from lignocellulosic feedstock such as straw of cereal crops, biodiesel from used cooking oil, biodiesel from oil energy crops and hydrotreated vegetable oil. The sector of motor biofuels still is at an early stage of development in Ukraine. Thus, the scientific novelty is that the recommended technologies indicate a possible way for solving some urgent environmental and energy problems, in particular, reduction of GHG and exhaust gases emissions, utilization of waste and residues, saving of expensive fossil fuels. The focus is expected to be on advanced biofuels as they can solve the mentioned problems more efficiently.

Ukraine has enough biomass to produce first- and second-generation biofuels for domestic market and for export. To promote the production and consumption of motor biofuels we recommend an early approval of the draft National Energy and Climate Plan of Ukraine for 2025-2030 as the Plan sets quite ambitious goals for the development of motor biofuels sector. In addition, we consider it necessary to adopt an existing draft Law that envisages the introduction of an obligatory share of biofuels in transport. The draft Law was registered in Ukrainian Parliament as far back as in 2020.

References:

1. Chiaramonti D. et al. 2021. The challenge of forecasting the role of biofuel in EU transport decarbonisation at 2050: A meta-analysis review of published scenarios. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 139, 110715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110715>
2. Delavarrafiee M., Frey H.C. 2018. Real-world fuel use and gaseous emission rates for flex fuel vehicles operated on E85 versus gasoline. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association*, 68(3), 235-254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2017.1405097>
3. Dusser P. 2019. The European Energy Policy for 2020–2030 RED II: what future for vegetable oil as a source of bioenergy? *OCL*, 26, 51. <https://doi.org/10.1051/ocl/2019040>
4. Geletukha G., Zheliezna T. 2021. Prospects for Bioenergy Development in Ukraine: Roadmap until 2050. *Ecological Engineering & Environmental Technology*, 22(5), 73-81. <https://doi.org/10.12912/27197050/139346>
5. Geletukha G. et al. 2022. Analysis of actions for Ukraine to replace Russian natural gas. *Ecological Engineering & Environmental Technology*, 23(4), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.12912/27197050/149458>
6. Klimenko V.N., Suprun T.T. 2023. Analysis of synthetic renewable methane production technologies for implementation in Ukraine. *Eurasian Physical Technical Journal*, 20(2), 41-45. <https://doi.org/10.31489/2023No2/41-45>
7. Lundberg L., Sanchez O.C., Zetterholm J. 2023. The impact of blending mandates on biofuel consumption, production, emission reductions and fuel prices. *Energy Policy*, 183, 113835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113835>
8. Panoutsou C. et al. 2021. Advanced biofuels to decarbonise European transport by 2030: Markets, challenges, and policies that impact their successful market uptake. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 34, 100633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2021.100633>
9. Soo-Young N. 2014. Application of hydrotreated vegetable oil from triglyceride based biomass to CI engines – a review. *Fuel*, 115, 88-96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2013.07.001>
10. Temirbekova M.N., Wójcik W. 2021. Power-generating fuel based on the processing of municipal solid waste organic components. *Eurasian Physical Technical Journal*, 18(3), 53-59. <https://doi.org/10.31489/2021No3/53-59>
11. Tryboi O., Zheliezna T., Drahnev S. 2023. Agricultural biomass feedstock for biofuels production in Ukraine. *Technium*, 14, 94-99. <https://doi.org/10.47577/technium.v14i.9686>
12. Tsakalidis A. et al. 2020. Catalyzing Sustainable Transport Innovation through Policy Support and Monitoring: The Case of TRIMIS and the European Green Deal. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3171. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083171>
13. Zheliezna T., Drahnev S. 2022. Comparative analysis of biofuels and other alternative fuels for introduction in aviation and waterborne transport of Ukraine. *Journal of Science. Lyon*, 37, 37-42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7409774>
14. Zheliezna T., Drahnev S. 2023. Current state and prospects for the production of motor biofuels in Ukraine. *Journal of Science. Lyon*, 42, 34-38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898728>
15. Zheliezna T., Drahnev S. 2024. Feasibility study of growing energy crops in Ukraine. *Journal of Science. Lyon*, 50, 46-51. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10610261>